

EFFECTS OF PROCESSING PARAMETERS ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES
OF SiC WHISKER REINFORCED ALUMINUM ALLOYS

YONEAKI FUJITA , HAJIME FUKUMOTO
Technical Research Center
Nippon Kokan K.K.
Kawasaki 210 JAPAN

and

YOSIYUKI KURITA
Planning and Coordination Dept.
Nippon Kokan
Tokyo 100 JAPAN

1. ABSTRACT

The influence of process and processing parameters, such as fabrication temperature, pressure and atmosphere, on the quality of SiC whisker reinforced aluminum alloys has been investigated in the squeeze casting method and the semi-liquid hot pressing method. Appropriate processing conditions are clarified for each process, and the squeeze casting method is selected as the most convenient process to obtain a high quality of composite. Tensile properties, such as Young's modulus, the tensile strength of a squeeze cast composite shows superior values and compression test results show reasonable formability. Furthermore, it is found that tensile strength and elongation are largely improved by extrusion and that those properties are not much improved by rolling.

2. INTRODUCTION

It has been demonstrated by prior investigations that SiC whisker reinforced aluminum alloys exhibit interesting properties, such as high modulus and high strength, which are attractive for structural application (1),(2). However, influence of processes and processing parameters, such as fabrication temperature, pressure and atmosphere in fabricating composite billets, on their quality has not been sufficiently documented. In present work, SiC whisker reinforced aluminum alloy billets were made under various processing conditions under the squeeze casting method and the semi-liquid hot pressing method. Their tensile

properties and micro-structures were examined from the above point of view. Furthermore, some composite billets were extruded or rolled and the effects of plastic deformation on the quality of the composite has been investigated.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3-1 MATERIALS

β -SiC whisker made by Tokai Carbon Ltd., used as the reinforcement (Table 3-1 and Photo 3-1). For the matrix materials, aluminum alloys, 6061, 2024 and 7075 were used. The volume fractions of reinforcement of the composite are mostly 20% in the present work.

Table 3-1 Properties of SiC whisker.

Diameter	0.1~1 μ m
Length	30~100 μ m
Density	3.19
Tensile strength	3~14 GPa
Young's modulus	400~700 GPa
Crystal phase	β -SiC

Photo 3-1 SEM image of SiC whisker.

3-2 FABRICATION METHOD OF COMPOSITE BILLETS

Fabrication procedures for the squeeze casting method and the semi-liquid hot pressing method are shown in Fig.3-1. The manufacturing process after preheating can be done both in air and vacuum (10^{-2} Torr) atmosphere in the case of each method. The billet size fabricated in this work is $\varnothing 50\text{mm} \times 60\text{mm}$ in both fabrication method.

a) Squeeze casting b) Hot pressing

Fig.3-1 Processing flow charts.

3-3 PLASTIC WORKING OF COMPOSITES

Some of the squeeze cast billets were extruded or rolled after homonizing heat treatment ($490^{\circ}\text{C} \times 10\text{hr}$ for 2024Al, 6061Al). $\text{O}16\text{mm}$ bars were extruded from $\text{O}50\text{mm} \times 60\text{mm}$ billets at $450 - 500^{\circ}\text{C}$. Extrusion ram speed is $2\text{mm}/\text{sec}$. On the other hand, $8\text{mm} \times 35\text{mm} \times 45\text{mm}$ specimens cut from the billets were rolled to 0.8mm thick sheets. Rolling temperature was kept between $450 - 500^{\circ}\text{C}$ and roll diameter and rolling speeds were $\text{O}100\text{mm}$ and about $50\text{mm}/\text{sec}$ respectively.

3-4 TESTING METHOD OF COMPOSITES

Tensile stresses and micro-structures were examined in the billets, extruded bars and rolled sheets. The shape of tensile specimens are shown in Fig.3-2. Tensile tests were done at both room and elevated temperatures ($200, 400^{\circ}\text{C}$). Cross-head speeds of tensile test was $0.1\text{mm}/\text{min}$. Compression tests were also carried out for the billets, to investigate the formability in the elevated temperature ($350 - 550^{\circ}\text{C}$). Compression specimen size was $\text{O}6\text{mm} \times 10\text{mm}$ and strain rate was 1sec^{-1} .

Fig.3-2 Shape of tensile test specimens.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSON

4-1 EFFECTS OF PROCESSING PARAMETERS ON QUALITY OF COMPOSITE BILLET (a) SQUEEZE CASTING METHOD

It is very important to remove entanglements of whiskers and air voids from SiC whisker preform to obtain high strength composites. The composites (20%SiCw./6061) made using homogeneous preforms show 500MPa tensile strength at room temperature and their micro-structures are homogeneous, as shown in Photo 4-1(a). On the other hand, the tensile strength of the composites made using roughly prepared preforms were below 300MPa and their micro-structures were not homogeneous, as shown in Photo 4-1(b).

Degassing from the preform during infiltration of melt aluminum alloys is also an important technical point, to obtain sound composite billets. It is found that the degassing can be attained sufficiently by using casting die with degassing vents. In the case where degassing vents were not used, micro-porosities remain in a squeeze cast billet (Photo 4-1(c)). The tensile strength of the composite billet with micro-porosities is lower than 300MPa. On the other hand, vacuum atmosphere is not so effective in improving the micro-structure and tensile strength of the billet cast in casting die with degassing vents.

The temperature of preform and liquid aluminum alloys should exceed 600 °C and 700 °C, respectively.

Tensile strength of the billet is stable when the consolidation pressure exceeds 100MPa. However, infiltration pressure is only 10 - 20MPa. So the preform should be prepared so as not to be destroyed under this pressure.

(a) using homogeneous preform (b) using roughly prepared preform (c) squeeze cast in die without vents

Photo 4-1 Micro-structure of squeeze cast billets (20%SiCw./6061).

(b) SEMI-LIQUID HOT PRESSING METHOD

A preparation of homogeneous mixture of SiC whiskers and aluminum alloy powders (as shown in Photo 4-2) is the basis to obtain sound composite billets. Untieing entangled whiskers and obtaining uniform dispersion was found to be attained by choosing an appropriate aluminum alloy powder size, and mixing in a jet air flow.

The tensile strength of the composite increases as consolidation temperatures become higher, and the highest strength (420MPa) is obtained when consolidation temperatures exceed the liquidus temperature.

Tensile strength also increases as the consolidation pressure rises, and it has demonstrated stability when the consolidation pressure exceeds 300MPa.

Atmosphere at the consolidation has a large influence on the quality of a composite billet. Tensile strength of a composite consolidated in a vacuum (10^{-2} Torr) atmosphere improves, as shown in Fig.4-1.

Photo 4-2 Mixture of SiCw./6061p.

Fig.4-1 Effect of atmosphere during semi-liquid hot pressing on tensile strength of composite (20%SiCw./6061-T6).

4-2 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITES

(1) CAST BILLET

(a) TENSILE PROPERTIES

Fig.4-2 and Fig.4-3 illustrate the results of tensile properties for composite billets (20%SiCw./6061, 2024 and 7075) made by the squeeze casting method under appropriate conditions. As shown in these figures, Young's modulus, yield strength and tensile strength are much increased, compared with base metals at room temperature. Although these values decrease as the temperature increases, they are high enough compared with base metals. On the other hand, elongation is very low (1.3-2.5%) at room temperature, but it shows 10% at an elevated temperature (400 °C).

Comparison of experimental tensile strength and Young's modulus with estimated values calculated by rule of mixture are shown in Table 4-1. To estimate those values, following formula are adopted;

$$\sigma_c = B \cdot V_f \cdot \sigma_f + (1 - V_f) \cdot \sigma_m \quad (1)$$

$$E_c = B \cdot V_f \cdot E_f + (1 - V_f) \cdot E_m \quad (2)$$

where, σ_c ; Tensile strength of composite

σ_f ; Tensile strength of reinforcement

σ_m ; Tensile strength of matrix

E_c ; Young's modulus of composite

E_f ; Young's modulus of reinforcement

E_m ; Young's modulus of matrix

Fig.4-2 Tensile properties of squeeze cast billet (20%SiC/6061-T6) and extruded bar (6061-T6).

Fig.4-3 Tensile properties of squeeze cast billets (20%SiCw./2024-T6 and 20%SiCw.7075-T6).

V_f ; Volume fraction of reinforcement

B ; Alignment factor of reinforcement

(3/8 for random dispersion)

In this estimation, SiC whisker's aspect ratio is assumed to be larger than the critical aspect ratio R (5~40) from eq.(3).

$$R = \sigma_f / 2T \quad (3)$$

where, T ; Interfacial shear stress between reinforcement and matrix

The estimated tensile strengths and Young's modulus coincide with those experimental values, assuming that the SiC whisker's tensile strength and Young's modulus are 3GPa and 700GPa respectively.

Table 4-1 Results of estimated tensile strength and Young's modulus of composites

Materials	Whisker	Matrix	Composite	Estimated value
Tensile strength				
20%SiCw./6061		320MPa	500MPa	480 ~ 1300MPa
20%SiCw./2024	3 ~ 14GPa	430	580	560 ~ 1390
20%SiCw./7075		530	620	650 ~ 1470
Young's modulus				
20%SiCw./6061	400 ~ 700GPa	70GPa	105GPa	86 ~ 109GPa

(b) COMPRESSION PROPERTIES

Fig.4-4 shows the formability of composites (20% SiCw./6061, 2024) made by the squeeze casting method.

Fig.4-4 Formability of squeeze cast billet.

A 20%SiCw./6061 cast billet can be deformed up to 60% without crack occurrence, in a temperature range of 400 ~ 500 °C. A 20%SiCw./2024 cast billet can be deformed up to 50% in a temperature range of 400 ~ 450 °C. A crack has usually occurred at the whisker free area on the composite surface as shown in Photo 4-3. So a composite without such a whisker free area in micro structure is expected to show much better formability. The relation between compression flow stress of composites and temperature is shown in Fig.4-5. 20%SiCw./6061 and 20%SiCw./2024 show a compression flow stress between 80 ~ 250MPa and 80 ~ 350MPa, respectively, in a temperature range of 350~500 °C.

Photo 4-3 Micro-structure of crack occurrence area (20%SiCw./6061).

(a) 20%SiCw./6061

(b) 20%SiCw./2024

Fig.4-5 Flow stress of squeeze cast billet by compression test.

(2) EXTRUDED BARS AND ROLLED SHEETS

(a) EXTRUDED BARS

As shown in Photo 4-4(a) and (b), the whiskers dispersed without alignment in cast billets are aligned along the extruding direction by extrusion, and tensile strength and elongation are improved 80-150MPa and

3 - 5%, respectively, as shown in Fig.4-6. These improvements by extrusion should be caused by the alignment of whiskers and strengthening bonding between whiskers and matrix aluminum alloys.

(a) 20%SiCw./6061-T6

(b) 20%SiCw./2024-T6

Fig.4-6 Tensile properties of extruded bar and cast billet.

(b) ROLLED SHEETS

Tensile strength and elongation of rolled sheets are 520MPa and 2%, respectively, at room temperature. They are not improved by rolling so much as extrusion because the whiskers are not aligned sufficiently to the rolling direction and decreased to 10 μ m in length by rolling, as shown in Photo 4-5.

Photo 4-5 Micro-structure of rolled sheet (20%SiCw./6061).

5. CONCLUSIONS

1) In the squeeze casting process, preparing a homogeneous preform and degassing from preform during infiltration are very important in obtaining a sound billet. Degassing can be sufficiently attained by using a casting die with degassing vents. The tensile strength of the cast billet has been stable when preform temperature, aluminum alloy temperature and consolidation pressure exceeded 600 °C, 700 °C and 100MPa, respectively.

2) In the semi-liquid hot pressing process, homogeneous mixing of SiC whisker and aluminum alloy powder and consolidation atmosphere have a considerable influence on the quality of composite. Consolidation temperature should be nearly liquidus temperature and consolidation pressure should be more than 300MPa. Tensile strength of the composite consolidated in a vacuum (10^{-2} Torr) atmosphere shows 10 - 20% higher value than that of the composite made in the air atmosphere.

3) Tensile strength and Young's modulus of the squeeze cast billets fabricated under appropriate conditions largely increased, compared with matrix aluminum alloys. On the other hand, elongation decreased to 1.3 - 2.5%. Tensile strength and Young's modulus coincide with the estimation values calculated by rule of mixture, when tensile strength and Young's modulus of SiC whisker are assumed 3GPa and 700GPa, respectively.

4) Formability tests show that squeeze cast billets can be deformed up to 50 - 60% reduction without crack occurrence in a temperature range between 400 - 500 °C.

5) Tensile strength and elongation is improved 100MPa and 3 - 5%, respectively, by extrusion. On the other hand, these properties are not much improved by rolling. This difference should depend on the degree of alignment and decrease of SiC whisker length by the plastic working process.

REFERENCES

(1) for example,
David L. McDonald and Charles A. Hoffman , "Microstructure and Orientation Effects on Properties of Discontinuous Silicon Carbide/ Aluminum Composites" , NASA Technical Paper 2302 , 1984

(2) for example,
Akira Sakamoto , "Fabrication for Silicon Carbide Whisker Reinforced Aluminum Composite" , 3rd Symposium of Basic Industrial Technology for Future Industries - Metals and Composites Technology , 1985 , p91..104